

Integrated germplasm improvement—tidal wetlands

Yield performance of some rice lines in acid sulfate soils of Indonesia

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We compared 17 IRRI rice lines, 5 Indonesian lines, and checks Kapuas and IR36 in yield trials during the 1991-92 wet season (WS) in acid sulfate soils at Terantang and Unit Tatas (Table 1).

Two seedlings/hill were transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing in 4- × 5-m² plots with three replications. Plots were fertilized with 90-60-50 kg NPK/ha.

IR13426-19-2, IR21820-154-3-2-2-3, IR24637-38-2-2, and IR31432-7-2 significantly outyielded IR36 in Terantang (Table 2). Yields in Unit Tatas were lower than those in Terantang

Table 1. Some chemical characteristics of acid sulfate soils at Terantang and Unit Tatas, Indonesia.

Characteristic	Soil (0-20 cm)	
	Terantang	Unit Tatas
pH	4.0	4.0
Total N (%)	0.2	0.4
Organic C (%)	2.9	2.8
Available P (ppm)	1.7	1.7
Exchangeable K (meq/100 g)	0.6	0.2
SO ₄ ²⁻ (%)	1.2	0.1
Al ³⁺ (meq/100 g)	13.3	14.2
Fe (meq/100 g)	6.4	6.2
Na (meq/100 g)	0.3	0.2
Particle size (%)		
Sand	0.6	1.0
Silt	69.3	62.0
Clay	30	37

because of the higher acidity stress, but 11 lines, including local check Kapuas, outyielded IR36. IR24637-38-2-2 and IR21820-154-3-2-2-3 performed well at

IRRN REMINDER

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. All field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

both sites and appear suitable for growing in tidal swamp areas with acid sulfate soils. We have selected them for advanced trials. ■

Table 2. Grain yield, maturity, filled grains/panicle, unfilled grains/panicle, panicles/hill, and plant height of some rice lines. Terantang [T] and Unit Tatas [U], Indonesia, 1991-92 WS.

Line/check	Yield (t/ha)		Maturity (d)		Filled grains/panicle (no.)		Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)		Panicles/hill (no.)		Plant height (cm)	
	T	U	T	U	T	U	T	U	T	U	T	U
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	6.2	4.3	116	124	109	104	25	23	18	12	98	86
IR24637-38-2-2	6.1	3.3	115	125	100	98	22	26	16	10	104	89
IR13426-19-2	6.0	2.8	116	127	99	78	20	27	17	12	91	82
IR31432-7-2	5.9	2.5	119	125	96	71	19	25	15	10	108	86
Kapuas (check)	5.8	4.1	117	125	122	112	12	25	15	11	92	90
BW267-3	5.8	4.1	116	123	123	101	33	29	14	11	112	101
IR6023-10-1-1	5.8	3.3	118	126	129	108	32	27	12	10	118	107
IR15865-430-3-1	5.8	3.1	113	123	98	78	20	25	18	10	99	86
IR33353-64-1-2-1	5.7	2.5	115	123	78	82	25	31	16	10	102	88
CR261-7039-236	5.6	2.1	117	123	134	97	24	26	14	10	102	86
B5344-Sm-61-2-1	5.6	2.3	119	129	109	84	55	42	13	13	107	100
IR51500-AC9-7	5.6	4.1	106	122	71	76	13	20	12	13	100	87
B5332-3d-Mr-84-3-1	5.4	2.0	121	126	93	82	21	32	15	10	116	101
IR9884-54-3-EI-P1	5.3	3.3	113	128	97	66	26	32	17	13	97	87
IR2071-105-9-1	5.3	2.3	132	129	121	80	29	31	13	11	108	96
IR31429-14-2-3	5.3	1.4	118	123	79	74	23	29	14	8	96	87
IR21567-16-3	5.3	2.8	127	122	74	82	34	22	15	8	84	82
IR21567-9-2-2-3-1-3	5.2	3.5	123	132	116	99	27	33	14	12	96	99
B6996d-Mr-5-3	4.9	2.4	118	125	69	92	23	28	11	10	100	87
IR11288-B-B-69-1	4.8	4.0	116	125	77	68	30	23	16	13	93	81
IR36	4.7	2.0	114	111	104	69	18	23	11	11	68	68
B6992d-99-KA-2	4.6	2.9	117	125	116	100	29	35	12	10	116	89
IR21836-90-3	4.4	2.1	123	129	85	58	21	45	13	11	101	98
B6992d-Mr-84-3-1	3.8	3.2	109	117	78	78	21	24	12	15	92	81
LSD (0.05)	1.1	0.9	5.4	2.4	35.7	31.3	13.1	11.6	4.2	2.9	8.6	9.1
CV (%)	24.2	18.9	2.8	1.2	21.9	22.3	31.8	24.5	17.9	16.4	5.2	6.2